

Synchronous Machine Salient Pole FRA Signature Modelling via Hybrid Methodology

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Abstract—Frequency Response Analysis (FRA) for rotating electrical machine diagnosis is not widespread despite its potential to detect a wide variety of faults and degradation mechanisms. The inspection and post-fault diagnosis of salient poles of MVA-range synchronous generators represents an emerging topic of research in this context. Up to date, FRA curve models are mainly data-based models or grey-box models oriented for power transformers. Despite physics-based models are more difficult to implement, they allow a better comprehension of the system. This comprehensive modeling of different faults eases FRA data generation, detection capabilities, and the understanding of fault mechanics. The present paper introduces a hybrid model exploiting the physical structure of the pole and the healthy broadband impedance measurement. The model is based on multi-conductor transmission line theory, where each conductor is separately modeled and parametrized. The model parameters are initially estimated via Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and then refined by utilizing a genetic algorithm (GA) optimization. The proposed method maps the main trends of a healthy FRA response up to 1 MHz.

Index Terms—Fault diagnosis, Frequency Response, Machine Windings, SFRA, Systems modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Frequency Response Analysis (FRA) is a well-known technique used in a wide range of applications in electrical and electronic engineering. Some of them are filter design, control loop stability analysis and fault diagnosis among others [1]–[3]. FRA devices inject a constant amplitude and variable frequency voltage signal—in fault diagnosis, it is common to perform a frequency sweep from 10 Hz up to 2/20 MHz—

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in the input terminals of the device to analyze, and then, it measures the voltage in the output terminal. Regarding the voltage drop and phase difference between input and output voltages, the transfer function, or frequency response (FR), of the analyzed device is estimated.

In fault diagnosis, FRA was utilized since the early 1980’s in power transformer condition monitoring and fault detection encouraged by the problems that appeared during their transportation from the factory to the operation place [3]. Due to its capability of observing small differences in the impedance of the electrical windings, FRA tests were performed in the windings before and after the transportation of the transformer in order to ensure that the device did not suffer any damage during the process. As FRA depends on the materials and geometry of the analyzed electric equipment [4], with this technique, faults such as disks displacements, interturn faults or ground faults among others [5], could be detected by comparison with a previously done fingerprint, i.e., with a FRA test performed with apparatus at healthy state.

The FRA technique has required expert operators that could diagnose the power transformer by visual inspection of the curves. In this field, new research are focused on FRA modeling and artificial intelligence (AI)-based fault classifiers design for power transformers in order to better analyze the high amount of information provided in the FR curves [3]. In [6], various ML models fault classification accuracy are evaluated against thermal, electrical and moisture faults at different frequency bands. In [7], a data-based model is implemented allowing the inter-turns fault detection with image processing applied in the FRA curves. However, data-based models require FRA curves of faulty devices, which can be considerably hard to obtain from already commissioned power transformers. Finally, Abu-Siada et al. estimated the parameters of power transformer winding through AI [8]. In this study, unitary one-disk equivalent models are connected

in series to form the transformer winding.

Despite FRA technique has been widely used in power transformers, its application in rotating electrical machines still be new and the literature about its use is scarce [8]. For this kind of machines, FRA can be used once the relays trip the protection in order to locate faults or can be used during programmed maintenance to do condition monitoring. In [9], a rotor pole of a synchronous machine is tested under healthy and faulty conditions. A data-based model is used and ground faults are located by doing two FRA measures, one by direct injection and another swapping the injection and recording terminals. In [10], a simple RL-series C-parallel circuit is used and fitted according to different experimental FRA curves. The RLC parameters plot a point in a 3-D diagram that allows the fault classification attending to the point cluster which it is part of. However, this model does not add physical significance for the FRA curves understanding. Afterwards, Z. Zhao et al. proposed a grey-box model in a 5-kW electrical machine for FRA interpretation [11]. The study proposes an equivalent lumped parameter circuit to be fitted with a genetic algorithm. However, only the low frequency zone is explored, the frequency-dependence of the parameters is not studied and only low power machines are explored, which considerably limits the capacitances and mutual-inductance phenomena in the FRA curves. In [12], another grey box model is fitted. This one considers four different frequency ranges for the parameters of the equivalent model. Finally, in [13], a single stator pole is modelled through an equivalent circuit and then it is used for quality inspection and fault diagnosis. The faulty FRA curves are also fitted according to the model and compared. Thus, variations in the parameters allow the fault identification.

Attending to the previous literature advantages and limitations, this paper focuses on the physical model of a 40-MW synchronous-generator rotor pole. The method proposes a lumped-parameter equivalent circuit to solve the FRA curve fitting. The circuit parameters are obtained via Finite Element Analysis (FEA), which provides an approximation of the RLC parameters by including the materials and geometry of the pole. A Genetic Algorithm (GA) is utilized to fit the solution to match a healthy experimental FRA curve. The combination of FEA and GA effectively overcomes the model assumption limitations and the inaccuracies induced by material properties or pole geometry. The process is iteratively performed until the healthy FRA is fitted. This research overcomes some limitations of the previously enounced methods, which are the following:

- Physical high-frequency modeling of a large geometry in the context of rotating electrical machines, where skin and proximity effects in all conducting bodies pose a computational challenge.
- Comprehensive turn-by-turn modeling, which enables the virtual emulation of a wide variety of faults.

The paper is divided as follows. Section II poses the main theoretical background and describes the overall process.

Section III presents the experimental work to obtain the pole FRA signature. Section IV tackles the parameter extraction via FEA. Section V describes the utilized GA and its boundary conditions. Section VI presents and discuss the main outcomes of the healthy FRA response and Section VII concludes the work.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND & METHOD OVERVIEW

The present section poses the modeling principles and pipeline of the proposed methodology, and introduces the salient pole specimen under test. Salient poles located in large synchronous generators consist of a coil wound around a laminated core that creates the excitation rotating field. The pole specimen is part of a 40-MVA 13.8 kV($\pm 5\%$) / 50 Hz salient-pole synchronous generator installed in a hydro-power plant. The coil is formed by single conductors with unique impedance characteristics depending on their geometry and relative positioning with respect the laminated core. The detailed representation of such conductors follows the principles of multi-conductor transmission line theory [14], where each conductor possess unique per-unit-length parameters (i.e., series resistance and inductance and shunt conductance and capacitance). The spatial dependency of the propagating voltage and current waves can be neglected if the wavelength is larger than the longitudinal dimension at the maximum frequency of interest and thus, each conductor can be represented by a lumped equivalent circuit.

The proposed methodology models each conductor as a lumped-pi equivalent circuit. The circuit includes series resistance (R_s), self-inductance L_s and mutual inductive coupling between turns. Additionally, the circuit includes mutual capacitive coupling between conductors (C_t) as well as capacitive coupling between conductors and iron core (C_o). Figure 1 shows the proposed equivalent circuit topology and its parametrization. Shunt conductance is neglected due to the complexity of its estimation using conventional numerical methods.

The parametrization of the circuit in figure 1 is initially performed via Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and two different solvers. This allows the initial quantification of all parameters including the frequency dependency of resistances and inductances. These parameters are assembled into matrices to cope the FEA parameter extraction with the circuit solver. An optimization loop is implemented to refine the parameters obtained from the FEA model, aiming to address limitations

Fig. 1. Lumped equivalent circuit and parametrization for the proposed model

Fig. 2. Hybrid broadband frequency modeling method pipeline

related to geometry, modelling assumptions, and material properties. This refinement is enabled by the availability of the experimental data from the healthy pole. The optimization loop includes the RLC parameter scaling, and the circuit solution via Modified Nodal Analysis (MNA) [15]. The simulated and experimental responses are input into a cost function which provides a numerical value to be minimized by a GA. The algorithm converges into a global minimum that represents the best possible solution according to the defined boundary conditions. Figure 2 shows the proposed pipeline for the broadband frequency impedance response of the salient pole. Figure 3 shows the salient pole under study and its 2D cross-section and parametrization. The model input data is tabulated in Table I.

Several assumptions are adopted to facilitate the proposed modeling approach. A single lumped-pi circuit per-conductor is assumed for the total longitudinal dimension of the pole. Mutual inductive couplings between different conductor layers are not considered. Additionally, mutual inductive couplings between conductors with different current directions are not estimated via FEA. These are only represented as a fraction of the mutual coupling among conductors in the same layer and different sign. The three conductor layers possess identical per-conductor parameters. End-winding is not considered. These simplifications are adopted due to simulation computational limitations and to provide an adequate model complexity/accuracy ratio. Furthermore, several material prop-

Fig. 3. Salient pole specimen (a) geometry parametrization with rectangular conductor detail, (b) real depiction

TABLE I
INPUT MODEL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
pole width	300 mm
pole height	435 mm
coil gap height	200 mm
coil gap width	90 mm
cond height	13.5 mm
cond width	4.5 mm
axial length	1475 mm
number of conductor rows	4
number of conductor columns	16
conductor insulation width	0.25 mm
lamination thickness	0.35 mm
iron conductivity (σ_{iron})	1.9 MS/m
copper conductivity (σ_{cu})	58 MS/m
low frequency iron permeability ($\mu_{r,DC}$)	200
insulation permittivity (ϵ_r)	3

erties are subject to assumptions. Insulation permittivity ϵ_r is treated as frequency-independent, and the iron core low-frequency permeability locus $\mu_{r,DC}$ is assumed in the initial magnetization region of the B-H curve.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To enable the fitting of the physical model to the FRA signature, experimental tests were conducted on a rotor pole as depicted in figure 4. The pole is extracted from the synchronous generator for examination and the measurement schematic is shown in figure 5. The pole (1) consists of three layers (2) with 16 turns each. At the same time, each turn is divided into four parallel-connected rectangular conductors. The pole is then connected to an FRA device, whose main parameters are summarized in Table II. As illustrated in figure 5, the reference (CH.N) of the FRA device (6) can be connected to the iron core of the pole (5) or left as a floating body. FRA curves obtained with the iron core connected to CH.N are more sensitive to ground faults. Meanwhile, FRA

Fig. 4. FRA experimental setup, (1) salient pole, (2) conductor layers, (3) input terminal, (4) output terminal, (5) iron core terminal, (6) FRA device, (7) laptop for acquisition, processing and signal storage

Fig. 5. FRA device connection scheme for testing the rotor pole

TABLE II
FRA DEVICE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	Magnitude
Frequency range	10 Hz - 20 MHz
Output Impedance	50 Ω
Amplitude	2.83 V _{pp} = 1 V _{rms} at 50 Ω
Number of measurement points	3201 max.
Accuracy (down to -50dB)	<0.1 dB
Accuracy (between -50 dB and -80 dB)	<±1 dB

curves with floating core are more suitable to detect inter-turn faults [16]. In the present study, the modeling process is focused on the configuration with floating iron core.

Figure 6 shows two healthy state FRA curves in impedance mode with module and phase separated into two graphs. The upper graph plots the module while the lower one plots the phase angle of the impedance. The two traces correspond to the healthy state measurements using the FRA by direct connection (i.e., following figure 5) and reverse connection, (i.e., switching the CH.A and CH.B channels to output and input terminals, respectively). This way, if both FRA curves are identical, the healthy state of the pole is validated. However, little divergences appear at high frequencies (around 10 MHz) because of mutual parasitic inductances of the fixture connection cables. Note that for electrical fault location, frequencies up to the range of 1-2 MHz should be enough [4], [9]. These curves are utilized for the fitting process to physically reproduce the model of the rotor pole.

Fig. 6. Experimental result, FRA curves under healthy state for direct and reverse connections of the FRA terminals

IV. PARAMETER EXTRACTION

The RLC parameters for each conductor are extracted by utilizing two different FEA solvers. The parasitic capacitances between each conductor and between conductors and core are extracted by utilizing an electrostatic solver while frequency dependent resistances and inductance are extracted by utilizing a magnetodynamic solver in the frequency domain [17] (see figure 2). As illustrated in Figure 7, the conductors in each layer are sequentially numbered: first from top to bottom, and then from left to right. The conductor tags are defined by two indexes corresponding to the row and column numbers respectively.

The capacitances are extracted in a per-conductor basis by imposing a unitary voltage excitation. The excited conductor induces a surface charge density in the surrounding conductive bodies, which represents the capacitance following classic formulation:

$$C = \frac{\rho}{V} \quad (1)$$

where C represents the capacitance between excited and surrounding bodies, ρ represents the induced surface charge

Fig. 7. Salient pole conductor layer numbering for parameter extraction and matrix assembly

Fig. 8. Capacitance matrix assembly following geometric numbering, x- and y-axis indicate the conductor indexes in a row-column logic

Fig. 9. Contour plot around conductor 4-16 with current density colormap and real flux lines for two different excitation frequencies (a) 1 kHz, (b) 10 kHz, where skin and proximity effects are clearly observed

density and V represents the unitary voltage excitation. Figure 8 shows the extracted symmetrical capacitance matrix for a single conductor layer. Diagonal entries contain the capacitance between conductors and the iron core, while off-diagonal entries represent the coupling between different conductors.

The RL circuit parameters are inherently frequency dependent due to skin and proximity effects. An adaptive mesh is required to properly capture this effect in the modeled conductors, which causes the computational time to dramatically increase for increased simulation frequencies. The skin depth

in the conductors for each excitation frequency is estimated by utilizing classic formulation:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi f \sigma \mu}} \quad (2)$$

where δ represents the skin depth in meters, f is the excitation frequency, and σ and μ represent the material conductivity and permeability respectively. The iron core is modeled following the approach from [18], where complex permeability is utilized to model the shielding effect caused by eddy current loops at high frequencies. The complex permeability is estimated by following:

$$\begin{cases} \mu_{eff}(f) = \mu_0(\mu_r'(f) - j\mu_r''(f)) \\ \mu_r'(f) = \mu_{r,dc} \frac{\delta}{2b} \left(\frac{\sinh(2b/\delta) + \sin(2b/\delta)}{\cosh(2b/\delta) + \cos(2b/\delta)} \right) \\ \mu_r''(f) = \mu_{r,dc} \frac{\delta}{2\mu_{r,dc}} \left(\frac{\sinh(2b/\delta) - \sin(2b/\delta)}{\cosh(2b/\delta) + \cos(2b/\delta)} \right) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where μ_0 represents the vacuum permeability, b is the lamination thickness, and $\mu_{r,dc}$ is the low frequency relative permeability, which is assumed as the initial material permeability before the linear initial magnetization area on the B-H curve (i.e., traditionally between 100 and 1000) [19]. Figure 9 shows the contour plots showing the skin and proximity effects at two different excitation frequencies. The single conductor resistances and inductances are extracted by exciting each conductor with a unitary real-valued current. The voltage drop induced in each conductor represents its resistance and reactance, which can be distinguished by separating the real

Fig. 10. Frequency dependent parameter samples, (a) Resistances, (b) Self- and mutual inductances

and imaginary components, respectively. Figure 10 presents the parameters of a single conductor, illustrating the frequency-dependent behavior of each parameter. Note that both inductance (i.e., self-inductance L and mutual inductance M) and resistance exhibit significant variations depending on the geometric positioning.

V. OPTIMIZATION PROCESS

The proposed optimization problem is set to minimize a cost function by utilizing a GA. This optimization algorithm is selected due to its inherent ability to map global function minima [20]. The GA is based in natural selection derived from biological principles. The algorithm defines an initial population for the optimized parameters, which is deterministically modified over different generations. The initial solution population is scored and scaled. Then, the next generation is derived according to different mechanisms such as elite children, mutation of previous points, and crossover solutions. The algorithm stops when the maximum number of generations is achieved or the minimum function solution reaches a stable point.

The minimized function is set to perform a curve fitting between simulated and measured broadband frequency amplitude. The function is defined as the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the model predicted and measured impedance amplitude. This is given by the average of the squared point-wise differences, ensuring that the cost is normalized by the number of data points. Thus, the MSE is defined as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i^{model} - y_i^{target})^2 \quad (4)$$

where N is the number of frequency points, and y_i^{model} , y_i^{target} represent the discrete amplitudes of the modeled and measured curves for the i -th sample.

The optimization problem is set to tune the RLC parameters in the circuit. Six different parameters are scaled, which are the conductor-to-iron capacitive coupling, the inter-conductor capacitance, the inter-layer capacitance, conductor self-inductances, mutual-inductances, and the full resistance matrix. The problem lower and upper boundaries are defined between 0.1 and 3 respectively to allow physically meaningful scaling. The problem considers a maximum number of 500 generations, with a population size of 20, and a gaussian mutation function that enforces only positive parameter generation. Figure 11 shows the optimization problem evolution over the 500 generations and the value of the six defined parameters. The optimization is performed considering all frequency points from 100 Hz until 1 MHz.

VI. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The outcome of the proposed modeling approach is shown in figure 12. Figure 12 (a) shows the problem solution prior optimization while figure 12 (b) shows the final hybrid response once optimization is performed. The optimized response exhibits substantially better agreement with the target data than

Fig. 11. (a) Optimization evolution over 500 generations, and (b) best solution locus, (c) Optimized parameter result

Fig. 12. Simulated vs. experimental healthy FRA signature, (a) before optimization, (b) after optimization

the initial numerical prediction. This is clearly observed in the main resonance around 700 kHz. Additionally, the pure numerical solution displays different resonant behavior after the main resonance, while the optimized solution matches the number of resonances between 100 kHz and 1 MHz. However,

the frequency location of such secondary resonances are not precisely matched in terms of frequency location.

The main model disagreement is found in the initial inductive frequency band, where the optimized solution does not match the inductive slope. This may indicate a mismatch in the frequency evolution of the conductor resistance, which is purely scaled and maintains the relationships between the DC resistance and its frequency evolution. By contrast, the inductances vary only marginally between low and high frequencies, so any mismatch in its frequency response is comparatively minor. The mismatch in secondary resonance points may be caused by some of the model assumptions such as the identical parametrization of all conductor layers, or the absence of inductive mutual coupling between layers.

Note that the present modeling approach is constrained by two computational bottlenecks, which motivate the established assumptions. The first obstacle is found while computing per-conductor resistances and inductances due to the small skin depth and conductor dimension ratio, which results in a large mesh for each simulation. As an example, a simulation around 800 kHz, takes 140 seconds to obtain a single conductor solution (simulated in Matlab 2022b running in personal computer with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1065G7 CPU @1.30GHz, 16 GB RAM, no dedicated GPU). Moreover, the GA repetitively simulates a large circuit formed by 384 branches (i.e., 64 conductors, two coil sides, and three conductor layers) and 160 frequency points. Each circuit simulation takes around 64 seconds by utilizing parallel computation in the frequency loop and the previously described personal computer. However, once the healthy response is modeled, several faulty scenarios can be emulated by only modifying the equivalent circuit connections.

VII. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

The present work describes a hybrid methodology (i.e., combined deterministic and data-based estimation) to physically model the FRA signature of a synchronous generator salient pole. The physical and per-conductor nature of the model enables the emulation and detailed comprehension of several fault mechanisms. The method succeeds on matching the main resonance and behaviour of the healthy FRA signature. However, it presents some limitations motivated by computational constraints. Future work will be focused on overcoming some of the established assumptions and to emulate the effect of several faults in the FRA signature of the pole.

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